

THE ANALYTICAL, EXPERIMENTAL, AND NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF
THE CRITICALITY OF AN INTERLAMINAR DEFECT IN A COMPOSITE LAMINATE[§]

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Abstract

The problem of the analytical, experimental and non-destructive evaluation of the criticality of an interlaminar defect in a composite laminate is investigated. The interlaminar debond represents a subsurface flaw resulting either from the laminate curing process or from foreign object damage. The specific geometry under consideration is that of an artificially implanted defect between two laminae in a laminated plate in cylindrical bending subjected to transverse loading. An analytical model based on the Griffith energy balance criterion is developed to predict debond growth. Specifically, the fracture surface energy γ_a (akin to the energy release rate G) associated with debond propagation is calculated. A quantitative estimate of γ_a is obtained from static tests of AS/3501 $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{4s}$ laminate cantilever beam specimens containing an interlaminar defect. For the determination of the bounds on debond growth as a function of fatigue cycles, a "mechanistic wearout" approach is utilized. These bounds are determined from the failure model by utilizing the lamina and interlaminar properties which are functions of fatigue cycles. Fatigue tests are conducted for various S -levels (maximum/ultimate stress) for debonded $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2s}$ AS/3501 laminates and the debond growth with number of cycles is determined by ultrasonic inspection.

The propagation of the debond can also adversely affect the flexural stiffness. Such a reduction in flexural stiffness can result either in excessive deflections or a shift in the natural frequencies of flexural vibrations. Thus it is appropriate to consider the residual flexural stiffness as a measure of failure (though not catastrophic as one would expect in a strength failure). Hence, the NDE effort involves not only the detection of the debond and periodic inspection to measure the growth of debond as a function of fatigue cycles, but also vibration tests of the test specimens before and after debond propagation, in order to determine the first four characteristic frequencies. The predicted change in the frequencies are compared with the experimental results. In this manner, a criterion can be established to define laminate failure due to a reduction in natural frequencies. This corresponds to a critical size of the debond.

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Introduction

In evaluating the integrity of metallic structural elements, nondestructive inspection has focused upon detection of both surface and subsurface flaws and determination of an effective flaw size. Given the flaw size, classical fracture mechanics technology has been employed to predict rate of growth and the critical length which corresponds to failure of the element. For composites, determination of the influence of a given flaw geometry upon strength and stiffness is considerably more complex than for metals due to their inherent anisotropy and heterogeneity.

Until recently, there was no formal quantitative criterion for inspection of advanced composite materials. With the introduction of the Aircraft Structural Integrity Program (MIL-STD-1530A), a quantitative approach to inspection and damage tolerance has been evolved. Allowable flaw limits and damage growth rates must be determined to establish inspection intervals and the flaw characteristics which make repair mandatory. Thus, a technology to assess the effects of defects in composite materials should be developed. Inherent in this approach are three major activities; namely, (i) critical flaw identification and detection, (ii) analysis and ND monitoring of flaw growth, and (iii) establishment of critical flaw size as a function of stress levels, fatigue cycles, and environment.

Thus, in order to develop the nondestructive inspection technology for fiber-reinforced composite materials, it is necessary that the development of detection capabilities be coupled with development of the technology that is capable of assessing the influence of flaw geometry upon strength and stiffness. By coupling the development of these two capabilities, it will be possible to define critical flaw geometries and thereby focus development of detection techniques for those geometries. To that end, the problem of the analytical, experimental, and ND evaluation of the criticality of an interlaminar defect is investigated here.

The interlaminar debond represents a subsurface flaw resulting either from the laminate curing process or from foreign object damage. The specific geometry under consideration is that of a debond in a cantilever laminated plate in cylindrical bending subjected to an alternating transverse (bending) load (Fig. 1). An analytical model based on the Griffith energy balance

Figure 1. Tip Loaded Layered Cantilever Beam With An Interlaminar Debond

Figure 2. Effect of Crack Location on the Critical Delamination Load for a $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2S}$ Laminate

criterion is developed to predict the growth of the debond. Tests of AS/3501 $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{4S}$ laminate cantilever beams containing an interlaminar defect are conducted to obtain a quantitative estimate of the fracture surface energy γ_a . Subsequently, a methodology is evolved for the determination of bounds on debond growth as a function of fatigue cycles. This fatigue analysis approach is essentially a coupling of the 'mechanistic wearout' concept of fatigue and the debond growth analysis. Fatigue tests are performed for various S-levels for debonded $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2S}$ AS/3501 laminates and the debond growth with number of cycles is monitored by ultrasonic inspection. Finally, the first four fundamental frequencies of vibrations of the unflawed/flawed $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2S}$ laminate beams are evaluated analytically and experimentally in order to assess their viability as a NDE parameter.

Static Failure Analysis to Determine Critical Debond Size

Considering the complexity of the analysis which requires the determination of the stress field in the vicinity of the interlaminar debond in Figure 1 and the further complications associated with inelastic behavior in the matrix dominated modes of deformation, it is appropriate to utilize the Griffith energy balance criterion to predict onset of the growth of delaminations. According to this criterion, an adhesive or cohesive

Figure 3. Typical C-Scans of $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2S}$ AS/3501 Laminate Test Panels Containing an Interlaminar Defect

fracture would commence at a critical applied stress when the incremental loss of strain energy of deformation with increasing fracture area has just exceeded the work required to create a new fracture surface. Thus, one would calculate a fracture surface energy γ_a (akin to the energy release rate G) associated with the debond propagation. By the energy balance criterion, the relationship between the strain energy and the specific adhesive fracture surface energy γ_a for unit width of the beam is

$$\frac{dU}{da} = 2\gamma_a \quad (1)$$

The strain energy U of the debonded laminated beam can be obtained in a straightforward manner from the Timoshenko beam theory without performing a detailed stress analysis to consider stress singularities and inelastic effects. Such an approach has been discussed in references 1 and 2 and utilized in reference 3 for the growth of delaminations in a partially debonded layered cylindrical shell. Note, however, that the above analysis procedure requires that there is no interaction between the in-plane and interlaminar failure modes. Also, in the present investigation, the specific fracture surface energy γ_a has to be obtained from experiment.

Figure 2 illustrates a typical variation of $P_{cr}/\sqrt{\gamma_a}$ with the non-dimensionalized debond length a/L (see Fig. 1) for an AS/3501 $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2S}$ laminate. Two different locations through the thickness are considered. Each point on the two curves represents catastrophic propagation of the debond. Assuming that γ_a is a constant, it is obvious from the figure that the magnitude of P_{cr} decreases with increasing debond size. Also, P_{cr} is lower when the delamination is at the neutral axis than when it is offset from it. This is to be expected because the interlaminar shear stress which is primarily driving the debond is maximum at the neutral axis.

* The static experimental program was conducted primarily to design beam specimens with an implanted interlaminar defect such that failure would occur by the propagation of the debond in a self-similar fashion. In this manner, a quantitative estimate of the fracture surface energy γ_a can be obtained.

Typical C-Scans of AS/3501 $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2S}$ laminate panels containing the interlaminar defect are shown in Figure 3 and a photomicrograph of the debond is illustrated in Figure 4. The debond is formed by inserting a col-

Figure 4. Photomicrograph of an Interlaminar Debond (X400)

* The experimental program was conducted at the University of Delaware

Figure 5. Test Fixture for Static and Fatigue Testing

Figure 6a. Localized Failure Under the Point of Application of Load for a $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2s}$ AS/3501 Laminate Beam

Table 1. Failure Loads (P_{cr}) for Two Initial Debond Sizes in an AS/3501 $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{4S}$ Laminate Cantilever Beam

Specimen No.	Debond Size a, in.	Failure Load, P_{cr} lbs	Calculated γ_a , lb/in.	Mode of Failure
1	1.00*	715		Self-Similar Propagation of Debond
2	1.00	759		"
3	1.00	517		"
4	1.00	<u>583</u>		"
	Avg.	644	2.04	
1	0.50**	1045		"
2	0.50	1012		"
3	0.50	<u>1075</u>		"
	Avg.	1043	1.31	

* $a/L = 0.333$, $l_1/L = 0.333$

** $a/L = 0.1666$, $l_1/L = 0.416$

lapsed teflon sheet tube during prepreg layup. Figure 5 indicates the test set-up. The beam is simply supported and the load (which is distributed over a finite area to avoid local interlaminar failures) is applied at the center. Initially, a $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2S}$ layup was used for the AS/3501 laminate. For this laminate thickness, failure always occurred under the point of application of the load as shown in Figure 6a. Consequently, the thickness of the laminate was doubled and the new layup was $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{4S}$. Such an increase in the thickness precludes bending failures and increases the probability of debond propagation because the magnitude of the remote transverse shear stress is increased. This modification did indeed result in the failure of the beam specimens by the self-similar propagation of the debond (see fig. 6b). Test results for two initial debond sizes are summarized in table 1. The

Figure 6b. Failure by Self-Similar Debond Propagation for a $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{4S}$ AS/3501 Laminate Beam

average γ_a values obtained from the analysis/experiment correlation for the two debond sizes are also tabulated in the table. Since γ_a is a material property, its magnitude should be independent of the debond size. However, the discrepancy (2.04 lb / in. for a 1 in. debond size vs. 1.31 lb / in. for a 0.5 in. debond size) can be attributed to the limited number of tests performed.

Fatigue Analysis Procedure

The basic objective of the critical flaw identification problem is to determine whether the structure is fail-safe or damage tolerant. That is, catastrophic crack growth must be avoided. In order to understand this, the flaw or damage growth rate and the time (number of cycles) to its unstable propagation must be known. Also such information is essential to determine periodic inspection intervals for the inspection of in-service structural components. In this context, the ideal approach for the debond growth problem is the one developed in references 4 and 5. In this approach, as illustrated schematically in Figure 7, the crack growth laws are obtained from the analysis, rather than from the experiment. Debond propagation would then be determined from the failure model by utilizing the lamina and interlaminar properties which are functions of fatigue cycles. However, due to the fact that the static failure model described above essentially determines the relationship between applied load and unstable debond propagation, it cannot be utilized to obtain stable debond growth as a function of fatigue cycles. Consequently, a modification of the approach in references 4 and 5 is proposed here.

The methodology to obtain bounds on the debond size as a function of fatigue cycles is illustrated in Figures 8 and 9. First, the wearout rates for the AS/3501 lamina properties are assumed to be the same as those for a boron-epoxy lamina in reference 5. This is done primarily because of the lack of appropriate AS/3501 lamina data. Further, all matrix dominated properties are assumed to have identical wearout rates. Secondly, it is postulated that the fracture surface energy γ_a , by virtue of being a material property, is also subject to change with fatigue cycles. The wearout rate dy/dn is once again taken to be the same as the slope of the S-N curve for the matrix dominated properties. $P_{cr}/\sqrt{\gamma_a}$ vs. a/L curves are then drawn in Figure 8 for different values of fatigue cycles N by utilizing the appropriate lamina properties. An initial debond size of $a/L = 0.3$ is identified and the corresponding $P_{cr}/\sqrt{\gamma_a}$ is determined for $N = 1$. For any given S-level, the $P_{cr}/\sqrt{\gamma_a}$ can be calculated. For $S = 0.5$, as shown in Figure 8, a horizontal line is drawn intersecting the various $P_{cr}/\sqrt{\gamma_a}$ vs. a/L curves for different N . These intersection points (only one for $N = 10^7$ is seen in the figure) define the bounds for the debond size as a function of fatigue cycles and are plotted in Figure 9. Point B represents the size of a/L for failure to occur at $S = 0.5$ with no material wearout ($N = 1$). On the other extreme, point C represents the number of cycles to failure assuming no growth in the initial debond size. Obviously, the actual failure point D is at an intermediate value of N . In the figure, it is seen that the material wearout assumes significance only beyond $N = 10^6$ when the slope of the a/L vs. $\log N$ curve changes rapidly. Hence, from an NDE viewpoint, inspection of the component is mandatory at about $N = 10^6$ and the maximum permissible flaw size is, say, $a/L = 0.55$. Beyond that value of N , catastrophic failure may occur. Thus, although a da/dN curve (AD) is not obtained by this approach, bounds are established on a/L for various N . This enables the NDI specialist to ascertain the margin of safety of the composite structure after an elapsed time during service. In addition, the method is simple enough and requires no elaborate stress analysis or experiments. Further evaluation of this approach is necessary, however.

Figure 7. Schematic Representation of the Wearout Process During Cyclic Loading

Figure 8. Effect of Fatigue Cycles on the Critical Delamination Load for a $[0_4 / \pm 45_2]_{2s}$ Laminate

Figure 9. Bounds on Catastrophic Debond Growth

Figure 10. Debond Growth As a Function of Fatigue Cycles

Fatigue tests were conducted for various S-levels for delaminated $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2s}$ AS/3501 laminate beam specimens and the debond growth was monitored by ultrasonic inspection. The C-Scans for different values of N (S = 0.5) are illustrated in Figure 10. Note that the debond growth is initiated near the free edge and failure eventually occurs by its unstable propagation just as in the static case (Fig. 6b). The growth of the debond area with N is shown in Figure 11. No attempt has been made here to correlate the experimentally observed debond growth with the bounds in Figure 9 because of the lack of appropriate data.

Frequency As A Parameter In Delamination Problems

Another important objective of the present investigation is to be able to define failure appropriately. Should fracture, as defined by a certain flaw size, be defined as failure or should there be an alternative definition of degradation? An important reason why composites are used is their high stiffness and any reduction in stiffness will reflect adversely on some design constraints such as the fundamental frequency or flutter speeds. In this context and for the present problem, debond growth will lead to the degradation of the flexural stiffness in the laminated beam. Hence the residual flexural stiffness can be considered as a measure of failure (though not catastrophic as one would expect in a strength failure). To that end, an analytical/experimental study was conducted to determine frequencies of vibrations of AS/3501 $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2s}$ laminated beams containing an inter-laminar debond.

It has been demonstrated analytically in references 6 and 7 that for a partially delaminated layered cylindrical shell, the flexural frequencies

Figure 11. Growth of Damage Area With N

Figure 12. Cantilever Beam Vibration Test Set-up

decrease significantly as compared to the case when there is no debond. For the present problem, the Timoshenko beam theory was used to obtain frequencies of vibrations of the delaminated beam (Fig. 1). Tests (see Fig. 12) were also performed to obtain the first four natural frequencies of vibrations, before and after fatigue cycling. Figure 13 illustrates the Chladni patterns for the third and fourth natural frequencies of the cantilever beam. Comparison of the analytical and experimental results are made in Table 2. It is seen that for no debond ($a/L = 0.0$), the agreement is excellent. However, for $a/L = 0.2$, the analytical predictions are consistently lower than the experimental values indicating that the residual flexural stiffness is higher than what is predicted. A possible reason for this discrepancy at higher frequencies could be due to the fact that the corresponding mode shapes do not coincide with the experimentally observed mode shapes. Hence the eigenvectors should be obtained for the eigenvalues in order to be able to make the right comparisons.

Conclusions

In summary, analytical, experimental and NDE problem of an interlaminar defect in a composite laminate was investigated. An analysis method based on the Griffith energy balance criterion was developed to determine onset of debond propagation in a laminated beam. A new methodology based on the "mechanistic wearout" concept was evolved to obtain bounds on catastrophic debond growth as a function of fatigue cycles. While this approach falls short of the determination of a debond growth law, it does provide a useful analytical tool for the NDE specialist. Static and fatigue tests were also conducted for AS/3501 $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2S}$ and $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{4S}$ laminate beams containing an interlaminar defect. An estimate of the fracture surface energy γ_a was obtained from the static tests. Damage growth during fatigue was monitored by ultrasonic inspection. Finally, an analytical/experimental vibration study was performed to ascertain the relationship between debond growth and residual flexural stiffness as measured by the frequency. Since no specific correlation was obtained because of the limited number of experiments, further investigation is necessary in order to be able to establish a relationship between a lower bound on the residual stiffness and flaw size.

Table 2. Comparison of Analytical and Experimental Values of Frequencies for a Debonded AS/3501 $[0_4/\pm 45_2]_{2S}$ Laminate Cantilever Beam

Frequency, (H_z)	<u>a/L = 0.0</u>		<u>a/L = 0.2*</u>	
	Analysis	Experiment	Analysis	Experiment
ω_1	313	342	207	340
ω_2	1,958	2,049	1,395	1,961
ω_3	5,483	5,407	3,918	5,351
ω_4	10,745	10,343	7,226	9,603

* $\omega_1/L = 0.2$

3rd Mode

4th Mode

Figure 13 Chladni Patterns for a Vibrating AS/3501
[04/±45₂]_{2s} Laminate Cantilever Beam

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